

Adverse soils tolerance

Effect of acidity on germination and growth of rice seeds

A. K. Bandyopadhyay, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Regional Research Station Canning, PO:Canning Town, Dist: 24-Pgs, West Bengal, India

Germination is an acute problem in coastal acid saline soils that remain highly acidic during the premonsoon dry period. We screened 118 IRRI germplasms in acid saline soils having pH 3.5. Nine varieties were selected.

A laboratory experiment was conducted to evaluate comparative tolerance of the selected varieties for graded acidity levels. Tap water (EC 1.0, pH 7.2) was used as the medium. Solution pH was adjusted to 1.0, 2.0,

3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, and 7.0 by adding hydrochloric acid. Ten seeds were kept in each solution in petri dishes, with three replications. Water volume was maintained by adding solution. After 4 d, the germinated seeds were counted and seedling height and root length

measured (see table).

No seeds germinated at pH 1.0 and 2.0. All seeds germinated at pH 3.0 and above except for CSR4 and IR28222-9-2-2-2-2. No variety produced root that could be measured at pH 3.0. BG35-2, BW100, B2149B-PN-26-1-1, and RD15 appear highly promising for coastal acid saline soils where germination is a problem. □

Effect of acidity (pH 3, 4, 5, 6, 7) on growth of rice seeds. West Bengal, India.

Variety	Seedling ht (cm)					Root length (cm)				
	3	4	5	6	7	3	4	5	6	7
BG35-2	3.5	6.3	6.0	6.0	5.7		5.5	5.5	3.5	3.2
BW100	4.5	6.3	6.7	6.0	5.4		5.5	7.0	8.0	8.5
B2149B-PN-26-1-1	3.4	6.7	7.7	7.0	5.4	T	3.0	4.0	4.5	3.0
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	1.2	7.3	1.7	6.2	6.3	r	2.5	3.5	5.0	5.5
IR44	3.0	5.5	5.6	5.2	4.3	a	2.0	5.0	3.5	4.0
ITA230	1.2	6.0	5.3	4.5	4.5	c	5.5	8.0	6.0	7.0
Mahsuri	1.2	5.5	5.2	4.7	5.2	e	5.0	6.5	3.0	3.0
IR8067-41-1E-P1	2.7	6.3	7.0	6.5	6.0	s	2.5	2.5	2.0	2.0
RD15	3.3	6.2	6.3	6.7	5.3		4.5	4.5	2.0	2.0
CSR4	0.5	6.0	6.3	5.5	5.8		9.0	9.0	11.0	6.3

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils and soil characterization

Influence of soil texture on rice crop performance

M. A. Salam, Cropping Systems Research Centre, Karamana 695002, Trivandrum; and S. Subramanian, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We studied the performance of IR20 rice in two soils of different textures in pot culture under natural light during summer 1983 (Feb-Jun).

The soils were clay loam (42.4% clay, 30.2% silt, 23.4% coarse sand, 4% fine sand, 99-8-254 ppm available NPK, 0.7 ppm DTPA extractable Zn, 1.0% organic C, pH 8.2, and EC 0.3 dS/m) and sandy clay (23.6% clay, 6.8% silt, 26.5% coarse sand, 37.2% fine sand, 100-4-140 ppm available NPK, 0.4 ppm DTPA extractable Zn, 0.42% organic C, pH 7.8, and EC 0.17 dS/m).

Influence of soil type on root production and grain yield. Tamil Nadu, 1983.

	Root dry weight (g/pot)		Grain yield (g/pot)
	Tillering	Panicle initiation	
Sandy clay loam	3.43	6.44	15.7
Clay loam	3.98	7.39	21.1
LSD (0.05)	0.14	0.17	0.4
CV (%)	7.3	5.3	2.4
Difference	0.6	1.0	5.4
% increase	16	15	34

The crops received standard management practices and recommended nutrients. Root dry weight was recorded at tillering and panicle initiation. Grain yield was measured at 14% moisture. The differences in root production and grain yield are given in the table.

Root production and grain yield were higher in fine textured clay loam than in coarse textured sandy clay loam. Grain yield and root dry weight had significant positive correlation.

The better performance of rice in clay loam soil was due to enhanced root production. □

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